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Program Development for Enhancement of Teachers’ Supervisory Competency of Dual Vocational Education System in Educational Institutions under Vocational Education Commission

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Abstract

Teachers with good supervision skills can help bridge the gap between academic and practical, ensuring that students will gain the skills and knowledge which they need to succeed in their chosen fields. At the same time, it helps them understand how these skills are applied in real-life settings. Overall, teacher supervision competencies are critical to the success of dual education systems. It ensures that students are educated and have high-quality training and are ready for future careers. Therefore, the design of this research and development study on the teacher’s competency components, the needs and program development for enhancement competencies of Teachers’ Supervisory Competency of Dual Vocational Education System in Educational Institutions under Vocational Education Commission. The method of research and development was divided into 4 phases. The tools used were questionnaires, assessment forms, teacher-supervisor competency-building programs, and a semi-structured interview. The statistics used were percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The results of the research were as follows: The competencies of training experience supervisors were categorized as follows: a) Curriculum administration and learning management b) Personal and Professional Development c) Innovation and information technology in education d) Ethics and professional ethics of teachers e) Educational research. These findings imply that the implemented program effectively contributed to the professional development of teachers' supervisors, leading to improved supervisory skills and competencies.

Keywords: Teacher Supervisory Competency, Dual Vocational Education System, Program Development

1. Introduction

The development of the country in various fields should be developed in education as the priority since education is a process that enables human beings to develop their quality of life to be able to live in society happily. The

quality of learners is an important aspect that is defined in every level of education curriculum and is the ultimate goal of education management that wants to happen to the students after they have studied in the course. After the National Education Act of 1999 was promulgated, educational reform was a national agenda. There are a total of 9 categories in which every category in the National Education Act aims to maximize the benefit of the learners. Especially in Category 4, the educational management approach is a learning reform that is considered the heart of educational reform for the 21st century. The contents of this category cover principles, content, and educational management processes that are open to participate, to create new visions of teaching and learning both inside and outside the school system. Information about learning at “The learner is the most important” by the definition of the learning process that the learner is the most important. Aiming to maximize the benefit of the students. for students to develop to their full potential, and have skills in acquiring a variety of knowledge The learning method can be applied in real life, and all parties are involved in every step to develop learners. The teacher must pay attention to and let the learners develop the relationship between the brain (head), mind (heart), hand (hand), and overall health (health) diversity of intelligence. Organizing the learning process should provide a variety of activities to enhance the potential of each learner (Wiroj Sararattana, 2005).

The National Education Plan (2017-2036) of the Ministry of Education has established a production strategy and developed research and innovation manpower to build the country's competitiveness to allow educational institutes and educational institutions to produce graduates with expertise and excellence in specific areas of study. that corresponds to the needs of the job market, and developing countries increase the percentage of education institutions. dual system education and cooperative education, school curriculum in the factory according to the specified standard has increased, (Office of the Education Council, 2017). The National Education Act of 1999 and its amendment (No. 2) of 2002 have set provisions in various categories related to the management of vocational education in Chapter 3 of the Educational System, Section 15. There are three forms of education: formal education, non-formal education, and informal education. Article 20 Management of vocational education, vocational training shall be provided in public educational establishments. private educational institution establishment or by cooperation between educational institutions and business establishments This shall be under the law on vocational education and related laws and Chapter 5, administration and Management of Education. Part 1 Administration and Management of State Education, Section 34, the Vocational Education Commission is responsible for proposing development plans and policies. standards and vocational education courses at all levels that correspond to the needs of the development plan national economy and society and national education plans; promotion and coordination of public and private vocational education management, a resource supporting, monitoring, and evaluating the results of vocational education management taking into account the quality and professional excellence Vocational Education Act B.E. 2551, in terms of vocational education management, Chapter 1, General, Section 6 stipulates that the management of vocational education and vocational training must be educational. in professional areas in line with the National Economic and Social Development Plan and the National Education Plan to produce and develop manpower at professional, skilled, technical, and technological levels including raising the level of vocational education to be in line with the needs of the labor market by bringing knowledge in theory that is universal and Thai wisdom to develop the learners to have knowledge and ability in practice and have the competency to the extent that they can be used for a career in the form of a practitioner or a self-employed person. vocational education and institutions as provided in this Act. (Vocational Education Act, 2008)

Dual vocational education management is one way of vocational education management that arises from agreements between vocational schools or institutes and enterprises, state enterprises, or government agencies in terms of curriculum teaching measurement and evaluation that students take part-time in a vocational school or institute and take practical lessons in the workplace, state enterprises or government agencies for the benefit of manpower production and development, vocational education institutes or institutes can manage many forms of education in combination. Or that institution must focus on the management of the dual education system is important. (Vocational Education Act, 2008) From research on manpower planning to develop Industry and administration of Thailand Development Research Institute, it was found that the quality of vocational labor had weaknesses in 3 areas: knowledge about writing skills and reporting preparation, occupational expertise found that there was still a lack of professional skills and expertise, and morality and ethics found that lack of responsibility, not punctual, lack of love and being honest with the agency. In addition, management of vocational education is

limited to management of education, in cooperation with the private sector or establishments. Associated with direct experience in a career, the key point is that practical training is ineffective as it should be due to the shortage of training materials and tools, modern machinery and equipment. Effective career teaching requires practical training. Professional skills in the workplace were the actual workplace, the Department of Vocational Education at that time had set policies since the year 1990. Training in the workplace, in addition to having a trainer in the workplace to take care of the training, there must also be a teacher from an educational institution to supervise the training by supervision principles. It is a process that is correlated with assessing, developing, and supervising skills as if it were a guard (Bernard and Goodyear, 2004).

Therefore, supervision is very important. It is necessary to have a complete supervision process according to the elements, able to supervise closely, consistently, and continuously. The characteristics of important supervisors are: (1) Willing to represent the organization in motivating the supervised to work on their own, (2) can properly exercise the authority of the superintendent. (3) Be a good example to be a role model for the supervision recipients. (4) Accept the change of roles. Most supervisors must be practitioners before they become supervisors. (5) Necessary skills of supervisors must have technical skills, interpersonal skills, and management skills, as well as decision-making and problem-solving skills, etc. Supervision has been used to assist teachers and administrators in vocational instruction as well as other educational arrangements. Therefore, when the process is properly supervised, it will support the internship to achieve its objectives and it is smooth with students working in real situations upon graduation they can work and have qualifications that are desirable to the needs of the workplace. Internships are an important aspect of vocational training. It encourages students to increase their skills. Enhance the experience and professional development according to the real situation after training on the basics of working in educational institutions. Internships allow students to gain hands-on experience, and can work have the opportunity to work and use tools, a real working machine. In addition, it is to learn the problem conditions and how to solve problems that arise during the internship rationally, as well as to train students to be responsible, disciplined, and work with others to have a good attitude, to work and to be proud of the profession (Office of the Vocational Education Commission, 2008)

Besides, an internship in the workplace also solves the problem of inefficient education and training systems. Effective and not linked, the academic working group determines the direction of potential development of vocational education in the public and private sectors and discussed the problems with the vocational education system that education and training do not respond to the needs of entrepreneurs. Therefore, emphasis is placed on teaching and learning at the vocational level, emphasizing the integration of theory and practice, and application. By emphasizing learning from real practices in the workplace and the real world of work. (Ministry of Education, 2013). Internship supervision is a process that goes hand in hand with internships. Internships to be effective must be supervised or supervised by professionals, with internship supervision being a reciprocal process. While those who have experience in working to help the inexperienced in assessing, developing skills, supervising until being able to achieve the student internship objectives, Management of internships in the workplace, suitable persons for supervision are trainers, also known as supervisors from the workplace, and supervisors from educational institutes. A supervisor plays a pivotal role in driving the management of the dual education system. Therefore, supervisors responsible for internships or vocational internships must possess knowledge, skills, and attitudes related to internship supervision in order to consistently provide effective and efficient vocational training experiences. Considering the origin and significance of the issue, it has been identified that the production of skilled workforce aligned with the requirements of enterprises and national development is imperative. This is particularly important in the field of vocational education and technology, where emphasis is placed on producing manpower with vocational certificates, high vocational certificates, and bachelor's degrees in technology or operations. Such qualifications ensure the quality and value of vocational education, catering to the needs of both the labor market and enterprises.

Therefore, the researcher is interested in developing a program to enhance teacher supervisors, vocational training, management of vocational education in the dual system in educational institutions, under The Office of the Vocational Education Commission to be a guideline for educational institutions to form a program for enhancing the competency of supervising teachers for vocational training. Management of the dual vocational education system in educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission and those involved

have components of the development of programs to enhance teacher competency and vocational experience training. Management of dual vocational education system in educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission that can apply the management method of the dual vocational education system in educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission for further quality.

2. Research objectives

1. To study the components of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission.
2. To study current conditions desirable conditions and the need for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission.
3. To design and development a program for the enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency in the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission.
4. To study the results of implementing the program for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission.

Conceptual framework of Program Development for Enhancement of Teachers' Supervisory Competency of Dual Vocational Education System in Educational Institutions under Vocational Education Commission

Figure 1.1 presents the concepts and theories used in drafting the Program for the enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency in the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Vocational Education Commission.

3. Method of conducting research

Program Development for the Enhancement of Teachers' Supervisory Competency of Dual Vocational Education Systems in Educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission is research and development. The researcher has divided the research methods into 4 phases as presented in the following .

Phase 1 A study of the components of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, The informant group consisted of 5 experts by purposive sampling.

Phase 2 A study about current conditions desirable conditions and the need for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission.

2.1 Population: school administrators Head of Vocational Education Division, Bilateral System and Teacher Supervisor for Vocational Training Experience management of vocational education in a bilateral system of 429 educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission

2.2 The sample group is school administrators, heads of the vocational education division of the dual system, and teacher supervisors for vocational training experiences management of vocational education in a bilateral system There were 429 educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission. The sample size was 234 students using the stratified random sampling method. The sample group was determined using the ready-made tables of Krejcie and Morgan (Boonchom Srisa-at). , 2011).

Phase 3 Design and development program for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Vocational Education Commission. Informants in group discussions for the development of teacher competency-building programs for vocational training. management of vocational education in a bilateral system namely, 5 experts, obtained according to the specified criteria and a group of informants who are responsible for evaluating the program. (By evaluating suitability/feasibility/benefit), namely, 9 experts, obtained according to the specified criteria.

Phase 4 A study of the results of implementing the program for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of Vocational Education Commission, the informant group Including supervising teachers, vocational training experiences in educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission that applied for the program, 1 place, 15 people.

4. Conclusion

Program Development for Enhancement of Teachers' Supervisory Competency of Dual Vocational Education System in Educational Institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, The results of the research can be summarized as follows:

1. The results of the study of the components of the competency of a dual vocational education management coaching professional experience training system Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission consist of 5 components: 1) Curriculum administration and learning management 2) Self- professional development 3) Innovation and information technology in education 4) Teacher professional ethics and ethics 5) Educational research
2. Results of the study of current conditions desirable condition and the need for teacher competency, vocational training experience management of vocational education in a bilateral system Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission Current condition, teacher competency, vocational training experience management of vocational education in a bilateral system Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission. Overall, the average level is moderate. The desirable condition for teachers' competencies, vocational training experiences management of vocational education

in a bilateral system which overall was at the highest level and needed competency of teachers, vocational training experience management of vocational education in a dual system Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission can be sorted as follows; they are innovation and information technology in education, curriculum administration and learning management, ethics and professional ethics of teachers, self-development, and professionalism. and the last one is educational research.

3. The results of the development of a program for enhancing the competency of teachers, vocational training experience management of vocational education in a bilateral system Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission The results of the development of a competency-building program for supervising vocational training management of vocational education in a bilateral system under the jurisdiction of the Office of the Vocational Education Commission It can be summarized as follows.

3.1 Components of the teacher competency building program for vocational training experience management of vocational education in a dual system, There are 3 parts under the vocational education institutes under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, namely, part 1 introduction, part 2, manual for using the program to enhance the vocational experience supervisor competency. management of vocational education in a bilateral system Under the educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission and Part 3 Measurement and Evaluation Details are as follows:

Part 1 Introduction consists of the principles, and objectives of the program. Program content, development methods, and program evaluation,

Part 2 Manual for the use of the teacher competency building program for vocational training experience management of vocational education in a bilateral system Under the vocational education institutes under the office of the vocational education commission consists of principles, objectives, and development methods. Preparation of materials, equipment, media, and knowledge content and activities consisting of 5 modules.

Part 3 Measurement and Evaluation consists of measurement and evaluation methods. and measurement and evaluation criteria

3.2 The content of the development activities of the program consists of the learning content of the program consisting of 5 modules with the following components; Module 1 Curriculum Administration and Learning Management, Module 2 Self-Development and Professionalism, Module 3 Innovation and Information Technology in Education, Module 4 Ethics. and professional ethics and Module 5 Educational Research. Each Module has 5 development methods; 1. Training, 2. Self-study, 3. Self-development, 4. Study visit, 5. Practical Training Form and Method of Development Using a development period of 105 hours, there was a method to develop the competency of teachers, coaches, and vocational training experiences in the management of vocational education in a bilateral system under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission. By adhering to the development principle 70: 20: 10, i.e. learning from the program 10% learning from others 20% and 70% experiential learning to build knowledge, understanding, and deep and sustainable learning skills so that the trainees can apply it as a principle for continuous self-development (Continuous Self Development). There are a total of 4 development stages: Step 1, Pre-Development Assessment 2 hours. Step 2, Development 15 hours, Step 3, Integration with Operation 86 hours, and Step 4, A 2-hour post-development assessment, in which various methods used to develop the program include 1) training, 2) workshops, 3) self-improvement, 4) study visit and 5) on-the-job training and program evaluation, consisting of 1. Knowledge assessment before and after participation in the program 2. Evaluation during the development of program participants and 3. Evaluation of participant satisfaction in the follow-up and evaluation program after development.

4. Study the results of implementing the program for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of Vocational Education Commission, The research results can be summarized as follows:

4.1 Assessment before and after joining the supervisor competency program Develop teachers' competencies, supervising teachers, vocational training experiences management of vocational education in a bilateral system Udon Thani Polytechnic College. The results of the individual test scores of the vocational training supervisors Management of vocational education in a bilateral system, schools under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission found that the teacher supervisors had an average score before the development of 16.95 out of a full score of 30, representing 56.52% and the score after development was 24.64 out of 30, representing 83.10%, showing that the supervisors of Udon Thani Polytechnic College The post-development scores were higher than the pre-development scores. and passed the criteria of 80% of all.

4.2 Satisfaction evaluation results of the program for enhancing teachers, experience training Profession Vocational education management, dual system, educational institutes under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission Satisfaction level of the program for enhancing professional experience supervisors Management of vocational education in a bilateral system, schools under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission found that satisfaction with the Teacher Supervisor Training Professional Experience Program Management of vocational education, a bilateral system, educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission Overall, it was at the highest level. The considering each item, 9 items were at the highest level and 3 items were at the high level, sorted by the average from the highest to the lowest 3 order, namely, measurement and evaluation, introduction, and media/learning resources, respectively. The components of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Vocational Education Commission

5. Discussion

From the research results on program development for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, There were interesting issues that the researcher brought to discuss the results. can continue as follows

1. The components of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Vocational Education Commission, confirmed by experts Overall, it was at the highest level. This is consistent with the research of Pongsak Duangtha (2014) on the development of teacher professional competency in private schools under the Phitsanulok Educational Service Area Office of all 7 core competencies, the highest performing aspect is good service performance, The second place is discipline, morality, ethics, and professional ethics, The third place is teamwork. And the last one is self-development and work performance, it was found that the highest performance was the learning management and classroom management competency, the second place is learner-centered development and the third place is subject knowledge, And the last one is curriculum development competency. Analysis of teacher professional competency component structure model by analytical method The affirmative element corresponds to empirical data based on the teacher professional competency measurement model in 7 components of core competency found that the component weight Sorted from most to least as follows: 1) Psychology for Teachers 2) Teacher hood 3) Self-Development 4) Achievement Orientation 5) Teamwork 6) Good Service 7) Discipline, Morality and Ethics in Teaching Profession and Professional Competency Measurement Model Teachers in the competency of the line of 9 components found that the weight of the components, sorted from most to least as follows: 1) Teacher Leadership 2) Curriculum Development 3) Community Collaboration 4) Analysis, Synthesis and Educational Research for Learner Development 5) Educational Measurement and Evaluation 6) Language Technology for Teachers and Technology Innovation educational information 7) knowledge in subject content 8) learner-centered development 9) learning management and classroom management guidelines for the development of teacher professional competency.
2. Current condition, desirable condition and the need assessment for the program development for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, The current state of competency of vocational training supervisors management of vocational education in a dual vocational education system under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, according to the competency components of

the vocational coaching professional experience training in a bilateral system Overall, the current condition is at a moderate level. The desirable condition of the vocational training supervisor's competency. management of vocational education in a dual system Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission Overall, the desirable condition was at the highest level and the need for teacher competency, professional experience training management of vocational education in a dual system educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, sort the needs assessment from most to least: innovation and educational information technology, curriculum administration and learning management, and ethics and professional ethics of teachers, respectively. Due to the creation of a questionnaire on current conditions and desirable conditions about building teachers' competencies for vocational training experiences management of vocational education in a dual system educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission, study the concepts, principles, and methods of constructing questionnaires. It covers the components according to the teacher competency-building program for vocational training. management of vocational education in a dual system of educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission. and the questionnaire was presented to the experts for their opinions. which is accurate in terms of content and appropriateness, consistent with the research of Opas Sukwan (2019) has studied and researched the study of teacher competency of vocational teachers in Bangkok. It was found that the competencies of vocational education teachers should be promoted. It was found that the competencies of vocational education teachers should be promoted by; 1) Curriculum development and teaching and learning management for vocational teachers that promote professional competency development and 2) permanent teacher development to enhance the competencies of vocational teachers as needed by vocational teachers and there are many ways to develop competency, such as training, and enhancing experience in the workplace.

3. The results of the program for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of Vocational Education Commission, components of the program for enhancing teacher competency, professional experience training management of vocational education in a dual system Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission have 3 parts: Part 1 Introduction consists of principles, objectives of the program. Program content, development methods, and program evaluation, Part 2 Manual for the use of the teacher competency building program for vocational training experience management of vocational education in a dual system Under the vocational education institutes under the office of the vocational education commission consists of principles, objectives, development methods. Preparation of materials, equipment, media, and knowledge content and activities consisting of 5 modules. Part 3 Measurement and Evaluation consists of measurement and evaluation methods. and measurement and evaluation criteria The content of the development activities of the program consists of the learning content of the program consisting of 5 modules, consisting of the following components: Module 1 Curriculum Administration and Learning Management, Module 2 Personal and Professional Development, Module 3 Innovation and Information Technology in Education, Module 4 Professional ethics and ethics and Module 5 Educational research. Each Module has 5 development methods: 1. Training, 2. Self-study, 3. Self-development, 4. Study visit, 5. Practical Training Form and Method of Development Using a development period of 105 hours, there was a method to develop the competency of teachers, coaches, and vocational training experiences in the management of vocational education in a dual system under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission by adhering to the development principle of 70: 20: 10, which is 10% program learning, 20% learning from others, and 70% experiential learning to build knowledge, understanding and learning skills that are profound and sustainable. The development students can use as a principle for continuous self-development. There are 4 steps of development as follows: step 1, pre-development assessment, 2 hours; Step 2, development, 15 hours; Step 3, integration with operations, 86 hours; and Step 4, post-development assessment, 2 hours. Various methods used to implement the development of the program include 1) training, 2) workshops, 3) self-development, 4) study visits, and 5) practical training and program evaluation. It consists of 1. Assessment of knowledge before and after participation in the program, 2. Assessment during the development of program participants, and 3. Assessment of program participant satisfaction, monitoring, and evaluation after development (Follow Up and Evaluation) consistent with the research of Yod Anong Jomhongpipat (2010) research The development of the teacher development program for learning management leaders according to the educational reform approach found

that 1) Teacher Leadership Development Program, Evaluation, Evaluation, which are vision, principles, objectives, content, process, structure and evaluation evaluation. The process of the program is divided into 2 phases: Phase 1: Management Teacher Development Program; learn in simulation Which is a workshop with steps, namely the exploration of the previous experience joint planning stage The knowledge and understanding stage for conceptualization, the concept application stage. Phase 2: Field Learning Leadership Development Program It is a continuous development of teacher-leadership skills from Phase 1 in real situations for 1 semester. The steps are implementation, supervision, follow-up, feedback, and reinforcement. The strengthening seminar which consistent with the research of Chanokphon Juthasong (2016) has researched the development of a program to enhancement the learning management competency of teachers under the Office of the Promotion of Non-Formal and Informal Education found that the learning management competency of the teachers under the Office of the Promotion of Non-Formal and Informal Education developed with program components, namely; 1) Principles and concepts of the program 2) Objectives of the program 3) Format and method of development 4) Structure of the program 5) Content and essence of the program, consisting of 6 modules: 1) Creating and developing a curriculum for adult learners. 2) Knowledge based on learning content 3) Learning design for adult learners 4) Organizing a variety of learning processes 5) Media use and media development innovation in learning management and 6) measurement and evaluation, It took 180 hours. Development methods were 1) training/workshop training, 2) field trips, 3) coaching, 4) self-study, 5) brainstorming, and 6) group meetings. small The development process has 4 steps: Step 1 Pre-Development Assessment, steps 2 Development, step 3 Knowledge Integration, and Step 4 Assessment after the development of assessment results by qualified experts found that the usefulness, feasibility, appropriateness, and accuracy were at the highest level.

4. A study of the results of implementing the program for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions– had an average score before the development of 16.95 out of 30, representing 56.52 percent, and after development, an average score of 24.64 out of 30, representing 83.10 percent. The post-development scores were higher than the pre-development scores and passed the criteria of 80% of all. This is because The researcher used both quantitative and qualitative data to determine the guidelines for the program for enhancing the competency of professional experience supervisors. management of dual vocational education and inviting knowledgeable and capable speakers who have experience in enhancing teacher competency, vocational training management of vocational education in a bilateral system Let's exchange knowledge in getting developed. The vocational training supervisors who are under development have the knowledge and understanding of the vocational training supervisors consistent with the research of Kamol Riengthaisong (2017). The development of a vocational training program in the workplace to enhance professional competency. For students in the field of automotive technical work. The research results can be summarized as follows: Conditions for vocational training in the workplace. automotive technical field according to the opinions of vocational training instructors, the suitability was at a high level with an average of 3.69. According to the opinions of trainers in the workplace, suitability was at a high level with an average of 3.99 and according to the opinions of the alumni who graduated from the bilateral system, the suitability was at a high level with an average of 3.85 automotive technical field according to the opinion of the Vocational Training Supervisor There was a high level of suitability with an average of 3.71 according to the opinions of trainers in the workplace. The suitability was moderate with an average of 3.33, and according to the opinions of alumni who graduated from a bilateral system, The suitability was at the middle level with an average of 3.35. Vocational training programs in enterprises to enhance professional competence for students Automotive technical field consists of 4 main components: 1) roles and responsibilities of personnel in vocational training practices in the workplace 2) Operating budget 3) Qualifications of establishments accepting bilateral students 4) joint management between educational institutes and enterprises by cooperation between educational institutions and enterprises to the process of vocational training in the workplace by cooperation between educational institutions and enterprises to the process of vocational training in the workplace of students under the bilateral system of vocational education management standards t, students who graduated from the bilateral system automotive technical field have professional competency according to the specified curriculum, possibility of an in-house vocational training program to enhance professional competencies for students Automotive technical field

found that overall the probability was at the highest level with an average of 4.80, consistent with the research of Kitti Chantra (2015). Training curriculum for the development of a participatory performance assessment system of vocational teachers Research results summarized as follows: 1) The developed participatory performance assessment system of vocational teachers. 5 experts, it was found that the overall picture of the system was at a high level. 2) Efficiency of the training program, in which the researcher has applied the CIPP model, the results are summarized as follows: the notification of the results of the competency assessment has the greatest need for training. 2.2) Results of preliminary factor assessment Efficiency of theoretical training courses For the trial, it was 84.65%/82.96% and for the practice, it was 85.79%. 2.3) Evaluation of the efficiency of the training course from theory for the actual implementation of the training course, the value was 84.93/83.58 percent and the practical value was 86.89 percent, which was higher than the specified criterion. The result of the product evaluation found that the satisfaction of the supervisors and the assesses about the overall use of knowledge was at a high level, and consistent with the researched Chanokporn Juthasong (2016) researched the development of a program for enhancing the competency of learning management of teachers under the Office of Promotion. Non-formal education and informal education found that the results of the implementation of the competency building program manage teacher learning under the Office for the Promotion of Non-formal Education and Informal Education, it was found that (1) the results of the knowledge test on teachers' learning management competency The pre-development score was 16.95, representing 56.52 percent, and the post-development score, receiving an average score of 24.64, representing 82.12 percent. The results of the assessment of teachers' learning management competency before the overall development are moderate after development overall was at the highest level and (3) satisfaction assessment results of overall program participants in all aspects were at the highest level.

6. Suggestions for applying research results

Considering the research on the program for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of Vocational Education Commission. The key points for development were found as follows:

1. The development of information technology innovation teacher advisors should be given priority in applying knowledge to supervising vocational training experiences. management of vocational education in a bilateral system of Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission.
2. Should provide training and curriculum development on teaching and learning in a dual system for supervisors. Educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission continuously will result in the organization's greatest success.
3. Supervisors should apply the knowledge gained from self-development. applied to work in supervision, vocational training experience in educational institutions under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission

7. Suggestions for further research are as follows:

1. A participatory action research study for enhancement of teachers' supervisory competency of the dual vocational education system in educational Institutions under the Office of Vocational Education Commission.
2. Study the model of enhancing the competency of teachers, vocational education management professional experience and dual system that affects the quality of vocational schools in the digital age.

References

- Bernard, J.M.,andR.K., Goodyear. (2004). *Fundamentals of clinical supervision (3rd ed.)*. NeedhamHeights, MA: Allyn&Bacon.
- Boonchom Srisaard. (2011). *Preliminary research*. 9th printing. Bangkok : Suwiriyan.

- Chanokphon Juthasang. (2016). *Development of a program for enhancing learning management competencies. Under the Promotion Office Non-formal education and informal education*. Dissertation of Administration and Educational Development. Mahasarakham: Mahasarakham University.
- Kamon Riengthaisong. *The development of vocational training programs in the workplace for enhancing professional competency. For students in the field of automotive technical work*. Faculty of Education, Srinakharinwirot University.
- Kitti Chandra. (2013). *Training course for the development of a performance assessment system involvement of vocational teachers*. King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok.
- Ministry of Education. (2013). *Government Gazette: Regulations of the Teachers Council of Thailand on Teaching Professional Standards, B.E.2013*. Bangkok: Ministry of Education.
- Office of the Education. Council. (2017). *National Education Plan B.E. 2017 – 2036*. 1st edition. Bangkok.
- Opas Sukwan. *A study of teacher competency of vocational education teachers in Bangkok*. Faculty of Education, Srinakharinwirot University.
- Pongsak Duangtha. (2014). *Development of Teacher Professional Competencies in Private Schools under the Phitsanulok Primary Educational Service Area Office, District 1*. Dissertation of Sripatum University.
- Vocational Education Commission. (2008). *Vocational Education Act 2008*. Bangkok: Author.
- Yod-anong Jomhongpipat. (2010). *The development of a teacher-leader development program for learning management according to guidelines for basic education reform*. Dissertation in Educational Administration Leadership graduate school Sakon Nakhon Rajabhat University.
- Zainal Arifin. (2020). *The technology andragogy work content knowledge model framework on technical and vocational education and training*. Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn).